

The impact of classical Cepheids' companions on the extragalactic distance scale

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The extragalactic distance scale (also known as the cosmic distance ladder) is built up by a set of interlocked methods of distance determinations. Every method has its usefulness range and therefore must be calibrated with a preceding method in order to construct a homogeneous distance scale. For example, a large-distance method (e.g. Supernovae type Ia) has to be calibrated with a mid-distance method (e.g. classical Cepheids), and a mid-distance method with a short-distance method (e.g. parallax). Only then can the long-distance method be used to determine the Hubble constant: the value that holds the information about the age, size, content, and fate of our Universe, and that has recently been reported to be $H_0 = 73.04 \pm 1.04 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ [1]. The uncertainty on H_0 has accumulated from systematic and statistical errors associated with all the methods constituting previous rungs of the distance ladder, and can only be minimized by reducing these contributory errors.

Classical Cepheids in binary systems

Classical Cepheids (hereafter referred to as Cepheids) are the most famous mid-range distance indicators: they are abundant in the Milky Way (MW) and other galaxies, and the period-luminosity relation (PLR) they follow is considered universal and of superior accuracy to that offered by other types of radial pulsators. Still, the accuracy of the PLR can be improved with the better understanding of the factors that affect the intrinsic or apparent brightness of Cepheids, e.g. the effect of metallicity [2], or the effect of binarity [3]. Unlike the effect of metallicity, the effect of binarity has so far been only described in a qualitative way and lacked quantification.

The effect of binarity predicts that Cepheids with unresolved companions appear brighter than their single counterparts, due to the extra – and unaccounted for – light of their companions. Consequently, the PLR contaminated with binary Cepheids is *shifted upwards*, i.e. the zero point of the PLR moves towards more negative magnitudes, and as a consequence the distance measured using the PLR becomes smaller than its true value, and H_0 – larger.

$$\begin{aligned} \mu &\Rightarrow d = 10^{0.2(\mu+5)} \Rightarrow H_0 = v/d \\ \text{smaller} &\Rightarrow \text{smaller} \Rightarrow \text{larger} \end{aligned}$$

Theoretical and empirical studies agree that binary Cepheids constitute 60-80% of all MW Cepheids [e.g. 4, 5]; a similarly high percentage is expected in the Small and Large Magellanic Clouds (SMC, LMC, respectively.) However, up-to-date only about 6% of MW Cepheids, and less than 1% of LMC and SMC Cepheids are identified as binaries [6, and references therein]. This means that

the sample of binary Cepheids suffers from tremendous completeness bias, and renders impossible the estimation of the shift of the PLR due to Cepheids' companions from the observational data. This shift can, however, be estimated using synthetic data.

Synthetic population of binary Cepheids

A synthetic sample of binary Cepheids was created using a binary population synthesis code, *StarTrack*, which was designed to execute approximate evolution and binary interaction of 2×10^5 binary systems, and adjusted to classify as Cepheids stars that fulfill all the requirements of the filtering algorithm [6]. The resulting sample is free from the selection and completeness biases, and can be further subjected to statistical analysis. The effect of binaries is controlled by the *binarity percentage*, f_{bin} , which is a free parameter that can range from 0% (only single Cepheids) to 100% (only binary Cepheids.)

Synthetic single Cepheids accurately reproduce the slope of the PLR of the real Cepheids reported in the literature [see 6, their Tab. 2 and Fig. 6], while synthetic binary Cepheids accurately reproduce the “outliers” above the PLR, which are identified as binary Cepheids with giant companions [7]. Figure 3 shows the outliers and can be directly compared with Figure 3 from [7]. The agreement between real and synthetic data endorses the synthetic population of binary Cepheids as a reliable tool to investigate the effect of the Cepheids' companions on the PLR.

Figure 1: Period-luminosity relation for synthetic Cepheids in the LMC with $f_{\text{bin}} = 100\%$. Y-axis denotes the observed brightness in the Wesenheit index. Outliers (above 50% threshold) are binary Cepheids with giant companions, while the rest of binary Cepheids have main sequence stars as companions. Excerpted from [6].

Apart from the outliers, Figure 3 also shows binary Cepheids with main sequence companions (navy blue data points). Their contribution to the total brightness of individual systems seems negligible, since they all lie very close to the PLR. However, their cumulative brightness causes the PLR zero point to shift upwards. This shift scales linearly with the binarity percentage and is the largest in the visual domain (~ 0.05 mag for $f_{\text{bin}} = 100\%$) and the smallest in the near-infrared and the Wesenheit index ($\lesssim 0.01$ mag for $f_{\text{bin}} = 100\%$).

Implications for the extragalactic distance scale

In order to determine distance (more precisely, *distance modulus*, μ) from a reference galaxy (e.g. MW) to a target galaxy (e.g. LMC), one can simply calculate the difference between the zero points of the Cepheid PLRs in both galaxies. When calculating the distance modulus between two galaxies with unknown percentage of binary Cepheids, one needs to take into account three possibilities, depicted in Figure 1:

- (i) the reference (MW) and target (LMC) galaxies have only single Cepheids, resulting in the distance modulus μ_0 ,
- (ii) the reference galaxy has a larger binarity percentage than the target galaxy, resulting in $\mu_1 > \mu_0$,
- (iii) the reference galaxy has a smaller binarity percentage than the target galaxy, resulting in $\mu_2 < \mu_0$.

Figure 2: Visualization of three distance moduli (μ) between the Cepheid PLRs in the MW (navy blue) and the LMC (orange). μ_0 is the distance modulus between the PLRs constructed with single Cepheids only (solid lines). μ_1 and μ_2 show how distance moduli would change if the PLRs were constructed with 50% of binary Cepheids (dashed line).

The shift in the distance modulus, $\Delta\mu$, is the difference between the distance modulus from the reference

to target galaxy, relative to μ_0 , i.e. $\Delta\mu = \mu - \mu_0$. Since binarity percentages for the reference and target galaxies do not have to be equal, $\Delta\mu$ can be either a positive or negative value. A grid of all possible $\Delta\mu$ values as a function of f_{bin} is shown in Figure 2. Two most extreme values in the top and bottom cells of the diagonal (0.002 and -0.003 mag, respectively) show the *maximum systematic error* of the distance modulus, i.e. the maximum value by which the distance modulus is shifted if the “assumed” binarity percentage is 0% while the “true” one is 100%, and vice versa. A full analysis for other passbands (BVIJHK and Wesenheit index) is beyond the scope of this paper and will be presented in the future (Karczmarek et al., in prep.)

Figure 3: A grid of possible values of distance modulus shifts, $\Delta\mu$, as a function of binarity percentage in the reference and target galaxies, in the K-band.

The maximum systematic error of the distance modulus in the K-band due to binary Cepheids, $\Delta\mu_K = \pm 0.003$ mag, changes H_0 by only $0.025 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}$ (or 0.035%), which remains well within the 1σ uncertainty range of H_0 . This value indicates that the effect of Cepheid binarity in the K-band on the extragalactic distance scale and the Hubble constant is in fact negligible.

References

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